

MIGRATION PATTERNS OF IGBO WOMEN IN LAGOS, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The increasing number of women migrants into the migration stream that was hitherto dominated by men has made it pertinent for migration scholars to fathom the dynamics of gender and migration. Using qualitative and quantitative approaches, this paper examines the migration pattern of Igbo women in Lagos. Results show that most Igbo migrant women in Lagos are rural-urban migrant and mainly migrated in sequence. Most of the female migrants moved in stages (55%). About 86% percent of those who migrated from urban areas to Lagos and 41% of those migrating to Lagos from rural areas moved in stages before arriving Lagos. Stage-wise migration is associated with a highly migratory group and is an indication of positive motivation of migrants. Among the first-time movers, or those with no previous migration experience, about 78% had a rural origin, relative to only 22% who originated from the urban areas. Clearly, most of the Igbo female migrants to Lagos have rural origins. The search for greener pastures remained the underlying factor for adopting different sequence of migration.

Keywords

Igbo women, rural-urban migration, stage-wise migration, Lagos

1. Introduction

Population movement has captured the interest of researchers from different parts of the globe over a long time. Migration is a major component of population change and development and has been a normal occurrence since the beginning of human development (Udo, 1997). Today, migration has taken a diversity of forms involving various categories of people who are distinctively motivated to migrate. Female migration cuts across all cultures, societies and geographical locations. The volume of female migration differs based on the prevailing cultural and economic conditions in a country (Ndaye, 1999).

Globally, the proportion of female migrants has been rapidly increasing, rising from 41 million in 1975 to 95 million in 2005 (Bourguigon, 2006). The Nigeria Migration and Urbanization Survey (1993) shows that

51.1 percent of migrants are female (NISER, 1997). Every year, thousands of women move from the villages to the cities (Data, 2005)

Gender is an important factor in determining the type of migration available to an individual. Participation in the decision on whether to migrate or not is also influenced by gender. Perceptions and behaviour about migration are influenced by the position of the individual in the social world, of which gender is a major determinant (INSTRAW, 2007). The effect of gender is far-reaching that it calls for a more extensive research than merely examining the differences between the proportions of males and females who migrate. This is because gender affects virtually all aspects of the migration process—from migration decision to migration experience (Riley and Gardner, 1993).

Migration is not gender neutral (UNFPA, 2008), it is a selective process that affects individuals differently (Adewale, 2005). Male and female migrants face different opportunities, risks, and challenges. Gender sensitivity features prominently in all aspects of the migration process (UNFPA, 2008). Gender is a significant factor in determining the kind of job that is available to migrant men and women. Women experience migration differently from men (Unnaithan-Kumar et al, 2008). Socio-cultural constraints also affect migrant women in different ways; as a result, women are affected by migration in different ways than men. The experience of female migrants reproduces and reinforces pre-existing gender patterns that dominate and oppress women as gender is a basic factor that influences migrant labour market at destination.

Migration among Igbo women has changed in terms of direction and/or patterns. Migration in the area, which dates back to the pre-colonial period, has been a source of livelihood for Igbo women (Chuku, 2005), and the main reason for migrating was agricultural. Women moved to other areas within the region due to scarcity of farm land or fertile farm-lands. Also, the inheritance system of the Igbo contributed to women's search for farmlands to cultivate; the Igbo woman usually does not own land or inherit anything in her father's house. As a result, many women migrate to other areas where they can lease land for farming activities (Chuku, 2005). In other words, Igbo women were mostly involved in rural-rural migration for agricultural purposes. With the changing trend and pattern of migration, rural-rural migration is no longer the most common type of migration among women in the area as increasing number of them have acquired higher educational qualifications.

After the civil war (1967-1970), and with a declining interest in agriculture, Igbo women migrated into cities, urban areas and outside the region in search of urban employment and a better source of livelihood. This is mainly due to the fact that the rural areas could no longer provide employment opportunities that suit their new educational qualifications and skills. Migrating outside the region, most Igbo internal migrants moved to the southwest, of which Lagos is the main destination (Mgbeafulu, 2003). Given the visibly rapid increase in the number of Igbo female migrants in south western Nigerian, this paper examines the patterns of migration among Igbo migrants in Lagos.

2. Brief Literature Review

In recent times there has been a change in rural-urban migration as more women are moving into this form of migration that was hitherto dominated by men (Kymzer, 2009). Chamratrithirong *et al* (1995) in a study in Thailand have revealed that more women than men participate in rural-urban migration than other forms of migration. Their study provided evidence that most of the women are rarely moving with a husband or a male relative, but that they are moving on their own, independent of a man in search of job in urban areas.

Being married bestows some responsibilities as well as privileges on couples. The man, as the head, of the family shoulders most of the responsibilities. As a result, he goes an extra mile in meeting up with these responsibilities. Fulfilling the economic needs of the family most often leads men and women to migrate in search of greener pastures. Consequently, married men and women migrate to areas they believe to be economically viable or where their economic needs would be met.

Adesijiet *al* (2009) in a study of rural-urban drift in a rural area of Kwara State showed that most of the migrants were married and the need to provide for the family was a major factor that motivated their migration. Family needs could be a push factor in migration of family heads on whom the onus lies, thus female household heads are more likely to migrate to urban areas than non-female household heads (Pekkala, 2003). The search for greener pastures among married men and women which is not unconnected

with family needs have been found to influence international migration of skilled migrants (Oyeyemi, 2004).

Nevertheless, some married women migrate to urban areas to join their husbands. This is mostly among women whose husbands migrated to urban areas after marriage and first time pregnant women (Nedoluzhk and Agadjania, 2010). Fenglian (2011), in a study of marriages in China, concluded that most married male rural-urban migrants leave their wives at home but bring them when they are economically stable because of high cost of living in a city. Some married women migrants prepare themselves for employment before migration by acquiring skills in some kind of jobs such as nursing and teaching that could be needed in any locale; and in that way they increase their chances of employment (Hanson and Pratt, 1991). Others got trained in professions that are related to their husbands' jobs (Katz and Monk, 1993).

Marital status also affects return migration and/or urban-rural migration among women. Women who migrate to join their husbands face return migration if their marriage breaks. That is they might be forced to return to their origin in the case of break up. In other words, divorce could shorten migration duration among women whose migration motive was to join their husbands (Bijwaard and Doeselaar, 2012). This could be more on young and low income migrant women who solely depend on their husbands; and those that are yet to integrate with their host communities. Ofuoku (2012) has shown in a study of urban-rural migration in Delta State, Nigeria, that most of the migrants live with their wives. Put differently, couples are more likely to be involved in this form of migration than those who are single, divorced or widowed.

What people do for livelihood has been found to be a factor motivating migration and where they migrate to or the form of migration they involve in. Occupational differences exist in migration processes and outcomes owing to the dynamic process involved in migration and occupation (Nguyen, 2005). That is migrants' profession or skill before migration and/or the desired skills to acquire can be a factor in migration. For instance, researches have shown that rural-rural migration is dominated mostly by unskilled migrants who are mainly involved in farming activities and trading in agricultural related business activities (Otite, 1979). Ekpenyong (1984), in a study of migrant farmers, revealed that farmers from a rural origin seem to migrate to other rural areas where they can continue with their familiar trade, that is what they are used to. These are migrants who want to keep doing what they do in a different location where they believe would be more economically benefitting.

Apart from rural-rural migration, occupational differences have been found to influence rural-urban migration of migrant women traders, who migrate to urban areas or cities where they believe there would be a boost in their business activities (Hollos 1991; Ekesionye, and Okolo, 2012). The role women play in domestic service has been found to facilitate the migration of women into cities and accelerate their adaptation to urban life (Bras, 1998).

Occupation also shapes urban-rural migration. In a study in Ekiti State, Adebo and Sekumade (2012) have shown that investment in rural occupation is one of the factors motivating the urban-rural migration of most retirees' in the area. In Ethiopia, migrants who acquired agricultural based skill in urban areas have been found to migrate back to rural areas where they can have access to land and other agricultural resources at a low cost to practice their occupation (Burley, 1982).

Even in international migration, occupational differences exist. Shortage of health workforce in developed countries has been found to be the main factor in the international migration of health professionals from developing countries to developed countries (Grignonet *al* 2012; WHO, 2006). The highly skilled professionals have been found to engage in international migration than the less skilled in Ireland (Wickham, 2009). This shows that the skilled are highly mobile.

3. Methodology

Research Design

The study adopted a descriptive design. This provided opportunity of describing the patterns, of migration among migrant Igbo women in Lagos. To achieve this, both qualitative and quantitative methods were utilized. These enabled the researchers to collect rich and complementary data on the phenomenon.

The Study Area

The study was conducted in Lagos State, one of the states in South Western Nigeria. It shares boundaries with Ogun State in the North and East, Benin Republic in the West and the Atlantic Ocean in the South. Lagos was formerly the Capital of Nigeria, and could be regarded as the hub of economic and financial activities in Nigeria as it hosts the major sea port and almost all the headquarters of financial institutions in Nigeria. Most national and multi-national companies in Nigeria also have their main base in Lagos. There are numerous industries which can create job opportunities in Lagos. This no doubt makes Lagos a choice destination for people seeking employment opportunities.

In addition, Lagos is a foremost commercial city of Nigeria. International markets in the city create opportunities for business activities; thus, it is an attractive city for migrant traders. It could also be regarded as the hub of educational activities as it is one of the States that have the highest number of universities as well as other tertiary institutions in Nigeria. These attributes of Lagos could be a catalyst for migration to the City especially among the South-Eastern States as the city par excellence for doing business. The state is composed of indigenes and migrants of diverse ethnic origins, which represent all ethnic groups in Nigeria and non-Nigerians.

The Study Population

The study population comprised female migrants from the South-East geo-political zone of Nigeria residing in Lagos. This included migrant women from the five states of the South-East: Imo, Abia, Anambra, Enugu, and Ebonyi States, who have lived in the Lagos for not less than one year as at the time of the study. Both married and single women from these states were included in the study.

The Study Sample

The sample for the study was drawn from migrant Igbo women in Lagos, which included both married and unmarried women of South Eastern States. Using Conchran's sample size formula, a sample size of 630 respondents was used for the quantitative data. For the IDI, the number of interviewees was guided by theoretical saturation (Strauss & Corbin, 1998), which started occurring from the 20th interviewee, but for expediency interviewing stopped with the 25th interviewee. Six FGDs were conducted on the basis of six key group identities as follows: rural origin, urban origin, never married, married, migrated alone, and migrated in company of husband or relative.

The Sampling Technique

The Senatorial Districts were used to ensure that sampling covers the entire State. The Multistage sampling technique was adopted. In the first stage, simple random sampling technique was used to select two local governments from each of the three senatorial districts. This gave a total of six LGAs. In the second stage, in each of the six LGAs that were selected, simple random sampling was used to select ten census enumeration areas (EAs). This gave a total of 60 EAs. In the last stage, in each of the EAs selected, household screening was done to identify the houses where female Igbo migrants resided; simple random sampling technique was used to select the respondents if there were more than two in a selected household. IDI respondents were purposively selected from migrants who have lived for more than 5 years in Lagos. The criteria used for selection were whether the respondent migrated from urban or rural area, whether the migrant is single or married, and whether the migrant came on her own or came with a family relative or husband.

Method of Data Collection

Before data collection, Research Assistants were trained who assisted in data collection. The researcher and other experienced researchers in the area of gender and migration conducted the training. The training helped the Research Assistants to familiarize themselves with the research instrument and objectives of the study before going to the field. This helped the researcher to make sure that they understood all the questions in the questionnaire, so as to minimize error and enhance the quality of data collected. The training also enabled them acquire skills that helped them to effectively interact with the respondents. They achieved this by learning how to create a conversational atmosphere that breeds trust and openness. After the training, a pilot study was conducted to pre-test the instruments and ascertain how well the research assistants have mastered the instruments; thereafter, data collection commenced.

4. Results

Demographic Profile of Respondents

Table 1 displays the socio-economic and demographic characteristics of the respondents. Panel 1 shows that most of the respondents were within the age categories 25-29 and 30-34, with 22.9% and 19.0% respectively. The median age was 35 years. Panel 2 shows that the respondents were well educated; 57.7% had tertiary education and 32.0% had secondary education. The “other” category (13.3%) comprised those with vocational education and other skill-based certification. About one-half of the respondents were married, while one-third of them were single. The “other” category (16.2%) was made up of those who were widowed, separated, divorced, and those that were co-habiting.

The occupational distribution of the female migrants shows that about 37% of them were traders. This is followed by those who were in salaried jobs (29.8%). The artisans (14.3%) included respondents who were into fashion designing, hair dressing, event planning, and all other forms of self-employed activities. Panel 5 shows that about 30% of the respondents reported no monthly income; this is due to the fairly high number of students and the unemployed, as well as those who for personal reasons failed to report their income. About 28% of the respondents reported a monthly income of ₹50,000 - ₹99,999, and another 20% ₹100,000 and above. With respect to religion, almost all the respondents were Christians, with 90.8%. Only 6.7% and 2.5% of the women respectively belonged to Islamic and African traditional religion.

Table:1 Distribution of Women Migrants by Socioeconomic and Demographic Characteristics

Panel	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
1	<u>Age:</u>		
	Less 19 yrs	30	4.8
	20-24 yrs	86	13.7
	25-29 yrs	144	22.9
	30-34 yrs	120	19.0
	35-39 yrs	114	18.1
	40-44 yrs	76	12.1
	45 yrs+	60	9.5
	Total	630	100.0
	Median age	(35)	
2	<u>Education:</u>		
	Primary	6	1.0
	Secondary	202	32.0
	Tertiary	338	57.7
	Other	84	13.3
	Total	630	100.0
3	<u>Marital Status:</u>		
	Single	210	33.3
	Married	318	50.5
	Other	102	16.2
	Total	630	100.0
4	<u>Occupation:</u>		
	Unemployed	62	9.8
	Student	58	9.2
	Artisans	90	14.3
	Salaried jobs	188	29.8
	Trading	232	36.8
	Total	630	100.0
5	<u>Monthly Income:</u>		
	No income	196	31.1
	Less ₹ 21,000	68	10.8
	₹21,000 - ₹49,999	62	9.8
	₹50,000 - ₹99,999	172	27.9
	₹100,000+	128	20.3
	Total	630	100.0

6	<u>Religion:</u>		
	Christianity	572	90.8
	Islam	42	6.7
	Traditional Religion	16	2.5
	Total	630	100.0

Most of the participants in the in-depth interviews were within the age groups 30 -34 and 25-29 with 7 and 6 persons respectively. About two-thirds of them have tertiary education and are married. More than half of them have lived in Lagos for more than 10 years. Also, about one-half of them migrated from the rural areas, and 14 out of 25 migrated independently.

Patterns of Migration

Table 2 presents the distribution of respondents by place of origin. More than half of the respondents (58.6%) migrated from rural areas, while 41.4% migrated from urban areas. This shows that most of the Igbo female migrants in Lagos belong to the rural-urban pattern of migration.

Table 2: Percentage Distribution of Respondents by Place of Origin

Residence	Frequency	Percentage
Urban	261	41.4
Rural	369	58.6
Total	630	100.0

Another aspect of migration pattern is sequence of migration which is shown in Table 3. Nearly one-quarter of those who migrated from an urban origin were first-time migrants moving from urban areas to Lagos. The rest of them moved in stages: from one urban to another and then to Lagos, and from an initial rural origin to an urban area and subsequently to Lagos. About 37% belong to the former, and 49% to the later. Rural migrants are shown in Panel 2. About two-thirds of them did not have migration experience before coming to Lagos; 22.8% migrated to a rural area from where they came to Lagos, while 18.1% migrated from an urban area to a rural area from where they came to Lagos. These may include those who were born in urban areas who were forced to return to their rural origins due to economic problems or inter-ethnic and/or religious crisis.

Overall, the Table indicates that most Igbo migrant women in Lagos moved in stages (55%). About 86% percent of those who migrated from urban areas to Lagos and 41% of those migrating to Lagos from rural areas moved in stages before arriving Lagos. Stage-wise migration is associated with a highly migratory group and is an indication of positive motivation of migrants. Nevertheless, among the first-time movers, or those with no previous migration experience, about 78% of them had a rural origin, relative to only 22% who originated from the urban areas. Clearly, most of the Igbo female migrants to Lagos have rural origins.

Table 3: Distribution of Migrants by Sequence of Migration

Panel	Stages	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Migrated from Urban area		
	Urban → Lagos	63	24.1
	Urban → Urban → Lagos	70	36.8
	Rural → Urban → Lagos	128	49.1
	Total	261	100.0
2	Migrated from Rural area		
	Rural → Lagos	218	59.1
	Rural → Rural → Lagos	84	22.8
	Urban → Rural → Lagos	67	18.1
	Total	369	100.0

Further on the patterns of migration are the maps showing the States and the senatorial districts from where the migrants migrated. Most of the migrants migrated from Ebonyi State; next is Enugu State. In each of the States, migrants came from all the three senatorial districts.

Fig 2: Maps showing the States from where migrants migrated.

Fig 3: Map showing the senatorial districts from where the migrants migrated.

The qualitative discussions confirm that most of the migrants had migrated to other places before coming to Lagos. Some migrated to rural areas before coming to Lagos, while others came to Lagos from urban areas.

A few migrated to the rural area first, then to an urban area before coming to Lagos. Some migrated to urban areas in South Eastern Nigerian while others migrated to South Western Nigeria before coming to Lagos. Those who did not have migration experience before coming to Lagos comprise migrants who were born either in rural or urban area from where they migrated to Lagos.

Further probing reveals those who migrated to the rural area first, then to an urban area, before coming Lagos did so out of the burning desire for economic change. In their quest for a change, they chose to migrate to a rural area that they believed was better than where they were living. For some of them, however, though they first moved to a rural area, it really served as a heaven for them relative to their place of origin. Some interviewees who migrated first to a rural area before coming to Lagos narrated how their lives changed.

By the time I went to live in the rural area that was the best I could get at that time. Looking at where I was then, that rural area was even like an abroad (urban area) for me. I only desired a change, and the rural area was the only available change that I could get. (IDI 4/38 year old/ rural migrant)

.... that village [where she migrated to before coming to Lagos] was like a “savior” for me. It is true that it is a village, but that was like a heaven for me. I made some money there. It was there that I first touched [earned] five thousand naira of my own, and saved small money that I used when I came to Lagos. I also had the opportunity of coming to this Lagos from that village. (IDI 5/35 year old/rural migrant)

Migrants who migrated first to a rural area did so mainly for economic reasons. Some rural areas provide more economic opportunities than others, such as rural areas with tarred road and electricity. A participant in one of the FGDs narrated how the rural area she migrated to was far better than her village.

....the village [rural area] I migrated to before coming to Lagos was much better than my own village where I was born and bred. You know tarred road passed through Ihite [the village she migrated to before coming to Lagos] and that gave the village an advantage over Ogbunka [her own village]. Trading activities are more there than my village because of the tarred road. Travellers always stop to buy things, so whatever you buy from bush [interior villages] will sell and I made much money from selling along the tarred road. (FGD 1/Res 4/ Rural migrant)

Trading along the tarred roads in some rural areas provides opportunities that attract migrants to such areas. Roads such as Enugu-Port Harcourt high-way, Enugu-Nsukka express-way and East-West road among others attract migration to a village along the road. An interviewee who migrated to a village along the Enugu—Port Harcourt high-way recounted her experience trading along the road:

My first trading experience was along the high-way in Ezinnachi [a village along the Enugu-PortHarcourt high-way].I went to live in that village because of the business. We buy goods from the villagers and sell along the road. People always stop to buy. You know some specific food stuffs are sold at specific points along the high-way. I used to sell Uzuzu and Otasi [local vegetables] and I made lot of money from that before I came to Lagos. (IDI 6/29 year old/ rural migrant)

Some government establishments in some rural areas also attract migrants to such areas. Establishments such as educational institutions, Local Government Area Headquarters, government agencies among others act as pull factors for migrants from more remote villages into such areas. Some migrants who were “pulled” to rural areas due to some government establishments in those areas made the following submissions:

I migrated to Ufuma [the rural area] because that is where the Federal Polytechnic Oko Campus for preliminary studies is located. We used to sell to the students; the problem is that it is seasonal. Whenever the students were on holidays we were usually out of business and that could be very frustrating; if not for that, that was a very good business. I made some money in that business. (IDI 8, 27 year old rural migrant)

...for me, my migrating to Sambo [the rural area] is because it is along the express-way [along east-west express-way] and the National Youth Service Corps Orientation Camp is very close to it, so we always sell our goods to corps members and to travellers who will always stop to buy snail. (FGD 1 Res. 2 32 year old rural migrant)

However, some migrants who migrated from the rural areas never had migration experience before they came to Lagos. They were born in rural areas from where they came to Lagos.

....for me I am a village girl. I was born and bred in the village, and lived all my life there before I came to Lagos... (FGD 1 Res. 1 30 year old rural migrant)

...I lived all my life in the village; I decided to come to a big city like Lagos where things will be happening and where I will enjoy some structural facilities that are not in the village.... (IDI 2/28 year old/ rural migrant)

Some migrants who migrated first to other urban areas in the western part of Nigeria before coming to Lagos did it deliberately. Migrating first to other parts of Yoruba-land was one of the strategies they thought would help them in coping/adapting in Lagos. A respondent had this to say:

You know, Lagos is a very big city, a no-man's land. So you don't just come here straight; you have to go to other areas that are close to it to learn certain things that you don't know about the people before coming to Lagos city; you know that they are Yoruba. My brother, this is like swimming, you know that you don't first go to the big ocean to swim. (FGD 2 Res. 3. 30 year old. Urban migrant)

Also, there are those who came from other urban areas in the western part of the country not as a coping strategy. Some of them migrated as a result of job transfer, while others were born there. Two of the interviewees had this to say:

My coming from other urban areas in Yoruba was due to my job. My office transferred me to Lagos, so I have no option but to come; even Lagos is not my dream place to live. (IDI 21/42 year old/Urban migrant)

I was born and buttered in Akure, but when things were not moving as I thought, I had to move down to Lagos to see if God will answer my prayer [to see if there will be a positive change in what she is doing] (IDI 9/ 29 year old. Urban migrant)

5. Conclusion

The findings reveal that the migration pattern of Igbo women in Lagos is diverse. Though most of the migrants are rural-urban migrants and mainly migrated in sequence, they have different reasons for adopting the sequence of migration they adopted. Almost all the reasons have economic empowerment as an underlying factor. However, non-economic factor was the underlying factor for few migrants for adopting the sequence of migration they adopted. In sum, most Igbo migrants women in Lagos are rural-urban migrants and have different patterns of migration; mostly migrating in sequence.

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